

1 **Supplementary Information**

2

3 **SI Figure Legends**

4 **Figure S1. Differences in antibody recognition of the different aSyn variants. Related to**

5 **Figure 3.** Adjacent rat midbrain sections of high-titer groups were stained with human aSyn-

6 specific syn211 antibody (A-E) or for comparison with pan-aSyn-specific Syn-1 antibody (F-J).

7 Corresponding contralateral (intact, uninjected) sides are shown in panels A and F, respectively.

8 Scale bar, 50 μ m.

9

10 **Figure S2. Human/mouse mismatches at positions 121 and 122 do not affect the ability of**

11 **aSyn to form Proteinase K-resistant aggregates in rat striatum. Related to Figure 4.**

12 Striatal specimens of animals from the highest vector group were incubated in the presence of

13 Proteinase K for 0 min (B-E), 5 min (G-J), or 45 min (L-O) and stained for aSyn to reveal the

14 formation of digestion-resistant aggregates (arrows). The digestion of endogenous (and

15 therefore soluble) aSyn was monitored in the CA2/CA3 region of the hippocampus (A, F, K).

16 Scale bar, 25 μ m.

17

18 **Figure S3. Effects of human/mouse substitutions at position 87 on fibrillization rates of**

19 **aSyn variants. Related to Figure 5.** The formation of amyloid-like fibrils was monitored in

20 solutions of h-aSyn A53T and h-aSyn A53T/S87N (A), h-aSyn Chimera and h-aSyn Chimera

21 S87N (B), m-aSyn and m-aSyn N87S (C), or m-aSyn Chimera and m-aSyn Chimera N87S (D)

22 (35 μ M of each). The protein solutions were incubated at 37°C with constant agitation and

23 analyzed at various times for thioflavin T fluorescence. The graphs show the mean normalized

24 fluorescence (determined from 3 or 4 technical replicates in each experiment) plotted against

25 the incubation time.

26

27 **SI Tables**

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29 **Table S1. Membrane affinities and maximum helix content of aSyn variants titrated with**
30 **PG:PC SUVs^a**

Variant	K_d^b (μM)	ellipticity minimum ($\times 10^3 \text{ deg}\cdot\text{cm}^2/\text{dmol}$)	maximum helicity (%)
h-aSyn-WT	1.5 ± 0.4	-18.6 ± 0.8	50 ± 3
h-aSyn-A53T	2.5 ± 0.3	-20.5 ± 0.4	55 ± 2
m-aSyn	2.4 ± 0.2	-20.4 ± 0.4	55 ± 2
h-aSyn-Chimera	2.6 ± 0.2	-21.1 ± 0.4	56 ± 2
m-aSyn-Chimera	1.6 ± 0.2	-17.7 ± 0.3	47 ± 2

31 ^aValues (\pm standard error) were determined from the far-UV CD data in Fig. 7A using equations
32 3-6; the concentration of aSyn was $5 \mu\text{M}$.

33 ^bThe CD data obtained for each variant were fit to equation 3 with the N value (binding
34 stoichiometry) set to 160, the value obtained by fitting the h-aSyn-WT data to equation 3 without
35 any constraints on N .
36

37 **Table S2. P values for vesicle permeabilization data in Figure 7C^a**

Comparison	Time (h)				
	24	48	72	96	120
ctrl vs. h-aSyn	****	****	****	****	****
ctrl vs. h-aSyn A53T	****	****	****	****	****
ctrl vs. m-aSyn Chimera	****	****	****	****	****
ctrl vs. h-aSyn Chimera	****	****	****	****	****
ctrl vs. m-syn	****	****	****	****	****
h-aSyn vs. h-aSyn A53T	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
h-aSyn vs. m-aSyn Chimera	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
h-aSyn vs. h-aSyn Chimera	ns	ns	****	****	****
h-aSyn vs. m-aSyn	ns	ns	**	**	****
h-aSyn A53T vs. m-aSyn Chimera	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
h-aSyn A53T vs. h-aSyn Chimera	ns	***	****	****	****
h-aSyn A53T vs. m-aSyn	ns	**	**	*	****
m-aSyn Chimera vs. h-aSyn Chimera	ns	*	***	****	****
m-aSyn Chimera vs. m-aSyn	ns	ns	ns	ns	***
h-aSyn Chimera vs. m-aSyn	ns	ns	ns	***	*

38 ^aTwo-way ANOVA; *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001, ****p<0.0001.

39

Figure S1.

Figure S2

Figure S3

